

Strategy for the Development of Open Science at Berdyansk State Pedagogical University

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Introduction

The modern advancement of science requires new approaches to preserving, disseminating, and utilizing scientific knowledge. Open science serves as a key paradigm that addresses these challenges by ensuring transparency, accessibility, and reusability of research outcomes. Universities play a leading role in implementing the principles of open science, fostering a culture of innovation, integrity, and collaboration.

Berdyansk State Pedagogical University (BSPU) strives to integrate the best global open science practices into its activities. This aligns with both national goals, outlined in Ukraine's *Roadmap for Integration into the European Research Area*, and international initiatives, including UNESCO recommendations and the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) principles.

An essential benchmark for developing open science in Ukraine is the *National Open Science Plan* approved by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine (*Decree No. 892-r dated October 8, 2022*). The concept for the development of open science at BSPU harmoniously integrates the key provisions of this plan with international best practices.

This concept aims to create conditions for the implementation of open science as an integral component of the university's educational, scientific, and innovative activities. It will serve as a foundation for transforming scientific practices, expanding access to knowledge, and enhancing their social significance.

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Mission

The mission of Berdyansk State Pedagogical University (BSPU) in the context of open science development is to foster the creation, preservation, and dissemination of knowledge that is accessible to all, promotes innovation, drives societal development, and facilitates integration into the global scientific community.

The university aims to:

- ❑ **Ensure accessibility** of scientific results and knowledge through open access to publications, data, educational resources, and other intellectual outputs.
- ❑ **Promote inclusivity** by engaging all stakeholders in scientific activities, including researchers, students, the public, and businesses, fostering an ecosystem of equal opportunities.

- ❑ **Integrate into the global scientific space** by adopting international open science standards such as the FAIR and CARE principles, using open licenses, and participating in global scientific initiatives.
- ❑ **Become a regional and national hub for open science development**, stimulating innovation and professional growth, and addressing societal challenges through transparency and accountability.

Implementing this mission will contribute to the development of the university as a modern, innovative educational and research center that combines the best academic practices with the needs of society, businesses, and the international scientific community.

3 Vision

Berdiansk State Pedagogical University aspires to become a recognized regional and national center for open science, setting new standards for transparency, innovation, and social responsibility.

The university's vision includes:

- ❑ **Leadership in Innovation:** Developing and implementing modern open science practices to ensure high-quality research, increase its societal impact, and integrate into the global academic space.
- ❑ **Research Transparency:** Ensuring open access to research results, data, and methodologies, fostering reproducibility, global accessibility, and trust in science.
- ❑ **Support for Research Infrastructure:** Creating modern repositories, providing access to international databases, and offering tools for research data management.
- ❑ **Social Impact of Science:** Strengthening the role of research activities in addressing social, economic, and environmental challenges through the effective use of scientific achievements.

Open science at BSPU will serve as the foundation for:

- ❑ **Advancing high-quality research** in priority areas for the region and the country, including pedagogy, interdisciplinary studies, and applied research.
- ❑ **Enhancing international scientific cooperation** through participation in global research networks, joint projects, and international conferences.
- ❑ **Integrating science and education** by creating innovative educational programs based on the results of cutting-edge research.
- ❑ **Implementing citizen science**, allowing society to engage in scientific processes and promoting scientific achievements.
- ❑ **Creating an inclusive research ecosystem** that facilitates effective knowledge exchange between science, education, business, and society.

The university aims to become a key hub for scientific innovation in the region, fostering a new culture of scientific activity based on openness, responsibility, and trust.

Key Principles

The concept of open science development at **Berdyansk State Pedagogical University (BSPU)** is based on the following fundamental principles:

1. Transparency and Openness

- ❑ The university strives for maximum research results, educational resources, and data openness. Open access enhances the quality, reproducibility, and global accessibility of knowledge.
- ❑ All research results funded by state or university resources must be deposited in open repositories accessible to the public.
- ❑ The university adheres to the *Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information*, emphasizing the need for public accessibility of data, reports, and research findings.

2. Balance Between Openness and Restrictions

- ❑ The university follows the principle: "*As open as possible, as closed as necessary*," recognizing that complete openness is achievable only within ethical, legal, and commercial constraints.
- ❑ Research results may remain restricted only when necessary to protect confidentiality, intellectual property rights, or other legitimate reasons.

3. FAIR and CARE Principles

- ❑ **FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable):** The university supports the preservation, publication, and utilization of scientific data in line with FAIR principles, ensuring their accessibility and reusability.
- ❑ **CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics):** The university guarantees ethical data use, respects the rights of researchers, study participants, and stakeholders, and ensures their involvement in research data governance processes.

4. Ethics and Integrity

- ❑ The university is committed to upholding high ethics, confidentiality, and scientific integrity standards. Special attention is given to human rights, sensitive data confidentiality, and personal information protection.
- ❑ Scientific activities must be based on honesty, transparency, and respect for ethical norms.

5. Avoidance of Predatory Journals

- ❑ The university enforces a policy to prevent publications in predatory or questionable journals that violate the principles of open science and scientific integrity.
- ❑ Research results should be published in journals that adhere to international quality, transparency, and openness standards.

6. Support for Open Citations and Bibliometric Resources

- ❑ The university supports the *Initiative for Open Citations (I4OC)* to ensure free access to citation data as an essential component of open science.

- Recognition of the importance of open bibliometric resources, such as *OpenAlex*, to improve transparency in evaluating scientific activities and ensure access to data that facilitates effective monitoring of research outcomes.

7. Implementation of Responsible Researcher Assessment Principles

- The university implements the principles outlined in the *Hong Kong Principles for Assessing Researchers*, emphasizing responsible evaluation practices covering all stages of research, from idea development to dissemination of results. Special focus is placed on transparency in research reporting, regardless of outcomes, and support for open practices (methods, data, materials).
- The university aligns with the approaches of the *Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA)*, which promotes qualitative evaluation methods recognizing researchers' contributions to open science and other aspects of their work.
- Adoption of the *San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA)* as part of university policy, emphasizing the importance of evaluating researchers based on qualitative indicators rather than quantitative metrics, such as the impact factor.
- Research assessment will include recognition of a broad range of contributions, such as replication, synthesis, meta-research, and contributions to the research ecosystem, including peer review, mentorship, science communication, and knowledge sharing.

These principles form the foundation for implementing the university's open science strategy, creating conditions for trust, accountability, and high-quality scientific activities.

Strategic Goals

To achieve its mission and realize the vision of open science, **Berdyansk State Pedagogical University** defines the following strategic goals:

1. Expanding Open Access to Research Results

- Publishing scientific works through the university's institutional repository and thematic repositories to ensure long-term preservation and access to research results.
- Engaging with international open-access platforms, such as **arXiv**, **Zenodo**, and **SocArXiv**, to globally present the university's research outputs.
- Integrating with initiatives of the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)** to ensure access to international infrastructures for data storage, processing, and dissemination.
- Supporting **open licenses (Creative Commons)** for publications and data to enhance their accessibility and reuse.

2. Implementing Research Data Management (RDM) Principles

- Developing **Data Management Plans (DMPs)** at the early stages of research to ensure a structured approach to data collection, storage, and dissemination.
- Providing access to research data through **certified repositories** that comply with international standards such as **CoreTrustSeal**.
- Training researchers in the **FAIR and CARE principles** for effective research data management.

3. Developing Open Science Infrastructure

- ❑ Establishing and maintaining repositories for scientific publications, research data, educational materials, and other scholarly outputs.
- ❑ Utilizing **open-source software** for data storage, processing, and dissemination to ensure system sustainability and scalability.
- ❑ Implementing **persistent digital identifiers (DOIs** for publications and data, **ORCID** for researchers, and **ROR** for institutions) to improve the visibility and identification of scientific results.

4. Integrating Open Science into the Educational Process

- ❑ Developing educational modules for students and researchers covering **open science principles, data management, and academic writing**.
- ❑ Integrating open science concepts into academic writing courses to develop skills in writing and publishing scientific works according to open-access principles.
- ❑ Preparing educational materials and manuals that demonstrate **practical applications of open data and resources** in the learning process.

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Key Objectives

To implement the strategic goals and ensure the sustainable development of open science, the university identifies the following key objectives:

1. Supporting Publication Activities in Open-Access Journals

- ❑ Providing informational and technical support to researchers for publishing in high-quality open-access journals that comply with international standards.
- ❑ Developing incentive mechanisms, such as grants to cover *article processing charges (APC)* in open-access journals.

2. Developing Partnerships with International Organizations

- ❑ Establishing partnerships with leading organizations supporting open science and participating in international initiatives.
- ❑ Actively engaging in programs like *Horizon Europe*, *COST*, and other international grant platforms.

3. Conducting Regular Training and Workshops

- ❑ Organizing training events for academic staff, students, and researchers on *Research Data Management (RDM)*, open access, licensing, and academic integrity.
- ❑ Creating open-access training materials in online formats, available to the broader university community.

4. Launching Citizen Science Projects

- ❑ Initiating projects that engage the public in data collection, analysis, and interpretation, promoting science communication.
- ❑ Developing platforms for interaction between researchers, students, and the public to address regional and global challenges.

5. Ensuring Integration of Open Bibliometric Resources and Citation Data

- ❑ Integrating data from platforms such as *OpenAlex* and *I4OC* into the university's research monitoring system.
- ❑ Using open bibliometric resources to evaluate research impact and promote university research outputs.

6. Implementing Principles of Responsible Researcher Assessment

- ❑ Integrating the *Hong Kong Principles for Assessing Researchers* into the university's research evaluation system.
- ❑ Developing guidelines to recognize a wide range of researcher achievements, including contributions to open science, mentorship, peer review, and science communication.

These objectives provide a practical toolkit for implementing open science principles, ensuring the integration of the university into the global scientific community.

Implementation Mechanisms

To implement the **Concept for the Development of Open Science at Berdyansk State Pedagogical University (BSPU)**, the following key mechanisms have been defined:

1. Organizational Structure

- ❑ Establishing an **Open Science Working Group** to coordinate the implementation of open science principles, monitor achievements, and develop recommendations.
- ❑ Appointing **responsible representatives** from each faculty to oversee the implementation of open science initiatives at the local level.

2. Financial Support

- ❑ Integrating open science principles into **grant applications** to attract additional funding and support research projects aligned with transparency and openness principles.
- ❑ Utilizing **national and international funds** to finance open science initiatives, including infrastructure development, staff capacity building, and science promotion.

3. Digital Tools

- ❑ Implementing **systems for managing publications and data**, such as institutional repositories, research data management platforms, and digital identifiers (*DOI, ORCID, ROR*).

Evaluation of Effectiveness

A system of indicators will be developed to monitor and assess the successful implementation of open science at the university. The indicators will analyze achievements regularly and identify areas for improvement.

1. Developing Open Science Evaluation Indicators

- ❑ **Number of open-access publications**, including articles in open-access journals, archived in repositories, and published under open licenses.
- ❑ **Number of developed open educational resources**, such as e-textbooks, presentations, educational modules, and video lectures.
- ❑ **Usage metrics of repositories**, including download counts, views, and citations of university resources.
- ❑ **Adoption of digital identifiers** (*DOI* for publications and data, *ORCID* for researchers, *ROR* for institutions) as an indicator of transparency and global integration.

2. Regular Progress Reporting

- ❑ Preparing an **annual report** on open science implementation, including quantitative and qualitative performance indicators.
- ❑ **Discuss results** at university events to involve the academic community in improving open science initiatives.
- ❑ **Publishing the report** on the university's official website to ensure transparency and openness.

This evaluation system will contribute to effectively managing the open science implementation process and enable the university to strengthen its position in the **global academic community**.

Final Provisions

Open Science is key to ensuring **transparency, accessibility, and innovation** in scientific activities. Its implementation enhances **research quality**, expands its **societal impact**, and integrates the university into the **global scientific space**.

Berdlyansk State Pedagogical University reaffirms its commitment to the principles of open science as a vital factor for **scientific and societal progress**. The university pledges to:

- ❑ **Promote the principles of open science** at all levels of its activities, from educational programs to research initiatives.
- ❑ **Develop infrastructure**, support researchers, and raise **awareness of open science** within the university community.

- **Adhere to ethical and legal standards**, ensuring the **confidentiality** of sensitive data, protecting **intellectual property rights**, and respecting **research participants**.

This **concept serves as a strategic document**, defining the university's direction for development as a **modern educational and research center**. It addresses contemporary challenges and contributes to the formation of a **knowledge-based society**.

Glossary of Terms

Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information: An international declaration aimed at promoting transparency, accessibility, and interoperability of research information through open standards, tools, and platforms for storing, sharing, and analyzing scientific data and metadata.

CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics): Ethical data management principles designed to protect Indigenous peoples' interests but applicable to all participants in scientific processes. CARE principles advocate for a fair and responsible approach to data management, ensuring openness and the protection of participants' rights.

Data Management Plan (DMP): A document outlining how research data will be collected, organized, stored, protected, and disseminated during and after a research project, aligning with FAIR and CARE principles.

DOI (Digital Object Identifier): A unique digital identifier used for the persistent identification and easy access to electronic scientific objects, such as articles, books, data, or other resources, regardless of online location.

European Open Science Cloud (EOSC): A European initiative to create a cloud-based infrastructure for storing, managing, analyzing, and accessing research data, facilitating collaboration among research institutions, scientists, and stakeholders within the European Research Area.

FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable): Data management principles ensuring that data are findable, accessible, interoperable across different systems, and reusable, thereby enhancing research efficiency and openness.

Hong Kong Principles for Assessing Researchers: Recommendations promoting responsible research assessment practices, emphasizing transparency, accountability, openness, replication, innovation, and contributions to the scientific community, including mentoring, peer review, and knowledge sharing.

Initiative for Open Citations (I4OC): This international initiative aims to ensure free access to citation data from scientific publications and enhance transparency, accessibility, and evaluation of scientific activities.

OpenAlex: An open database containing information about scientific publications, authors, institutions, journals, and research topics, providing bibliometric data to support open science and research evaluation (<https://openalex.org/>).

ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID): A unique and persistent identifier for researchers and authors, ensuring accurate identification of scientists across publication systems, databases, and repositories, preserving the integrity of their academic records.

Research Data Management (RDM): The process of managing research data throughout the entire lifecycle of a research project, including planning, collection, analysis, storage, archiving, and dissemination, in accordance with FAIR and CARE principles.

Research Organization Registry (ROR) ID: A unique identifier for research organizations created to standardize institutional references in research systems and databases, ensuring accurate identification and integration into the global research ecosystem.

San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA): This international declaration advocates for improved research assessment practices by shifting the focus from quantitative indicators, such as impact factors or citation counts, to qualitative contributions, including transparency, innovation, and societal impact.

Open Data: Data freely available for use, distribution, and modification without restrictions, provided that legal, ethical, and technical standards are met, enhancing transparency, reproducibility, and innovation in research.

Open Access: Free and unrestricted online access to scientific research outputs, including articles, books, data, and educational resources, allowing viewing, downloading, copying, and use under copyright compliance.

Open Science: An approach to organizing scientific research that ensures accessibility, transparency, and reusability of research outputs, including publications, data, methodologies, and educational resources, for all stakeholders.

Open Education: An approach to organizing the educational process that ensures access to knowledge and educational resources for everyone, regardless of location, time, or social status, through open technologies, tools, and teaching methods.

Open Educational Resources, OER: Educational, methodological, and informational materials freely available for use, modification, and distribution, typically under open licenses such as Creative Commons.

Citizen Science: A form of scientific activity involving public participation in data collection, observation, analysis, or interpretation of research results, enhancing engagement between the scientific community and society.

Open Access Journals: Scientific journals providing free online access to published articles, adhering to principles of open access, transparency in editorial processes, and licensing that allows unrestricted use and dissemination of materials.

Institutional Repository: A digital archive established by educational or research institutions for storing, disseminating, and ensuring access to research, educational, and creative outputs produced by their staff and students.

Creative Commons (CC Licenses): A set of open licenses allowing authors to define the terms of use for their works, supporting free dissemination, modification, and reuse while respecting copyright.

Meta-Research: The study of research methods, practices, and outcomes to evaluate their quality, transparency, reproducibility, and impact, aimed at improving the processes of generating and disseminating scientific knowledge.

Scientometrics: A scientific field analyzing the quantitative aspects of creating, disseminating, and using scientific knowledge through metrics such as publication activity, citation analysis, and other indicators for evaluating research performance.

Replication: The repetition of a scientific study to verify its validity and reproducibility, using similar methods, data, or experimental designs, serving as an essential component of quality assurance in science.

Thematic Repositories: Specialized digital archives storing and providing access to research results, data, and materials within specific scientific fields or topics, promoting their dissemination and use according to open science standards.

Predatory Journals: Publications mimicking legitimate scientific journals but failing to adhere to academic integrity standards, such as peer review and transparent editorial policies, focusing instead on charging publication fees without ensuring research quality or impact.